

Trippositive Silver Compounds of Piperazine Dibiguanide

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Complex compounds of piperazine dibiguanide with trivalent silver having the composition $[\text{Ag Pipz}(\text{BigH}_2)]\text{X}_3$, where $\text{X} = \text{OH}$, $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$ and NO_3 have been prepared and characterised.

Trippositive oxidation state of silver was stabilised by Ray and Chakravarty¹ in a series of complex compounds of ethylenedibiguanide, having composition $[\text{Ag} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{N}_5)_2]\text{X}_3$, where $\text{X} = \frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$, NO_3 , ClO_4 and OH . Silver (III) complexes with biguanide and methyl biguanide have also been reported by Sen².

During the present investigation three compounds of trippositive silver with piperazine dibiguanide *viz.* the complex hydroxide $[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}} \text{Pipz}(\text{BigH}_2)](\text{OH})_3$ (brown), complex sulphate $[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}} \text{Pipz}(\text{BigH}_2)](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 0.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (red) and the complex nitrate $[\text{Ag}^{\text{III}} \text{Pipz}(\text{BigH}_2)](\text{NO}_3)_3$ (reddish brown) have been isolated. Tervalent oxidation state of the metal in the complexes has been determined by oxidimetric titration. The compounds liberate two equivalents of iodine for every gram-atom of silver from acidified KI solution. The complex hydroxide and the sulphate are sparingly soluble in water whereas the nitrate is soluble. All the complexes are insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone, ether, dimethyl formamide and diacetone alcohol. The complexes undergo decomposition when kept for sometime in these solvents even in the cold and the dry compounds can be preserved unchanged in composition for a long time in the cold. The molar conductance value of the complex nitrate indicates that it is a tri-univalent electrolyte. All the compounds are diamagnetic and this serves as an added proof for the trivalency of the silver ion in the complexes. They may be represented as square planar complexes with dsp^2 hybrid bonds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Piperazine dibiguanide sulphate was prepared according to the method of Ray and Chowdhury³.

Silver (III) piperazine dibiguanide nitrate: Piperazine dibiguanide nitrate was prepared by triturating a slurry piperazine dibiguanide sulphate in water with calculated amount of barium nitrate. The mass was filtered and the clear filtrate on concentration in vacuum yielded colourless crystals of the dibiguanide nitrate. A solution of 2 g. of the dibiguanide nitrate in 50 ml. water was added to 0.68 g. of silver nitrate in 50 ml. water. To the mixture concentrated nitric acid was added followed by the addition of about 2 g. of potassium persulphate in 20 ml. water. The solution gradually turned red. After keeping about half an

1. P. Ray and K. R. Chakravarty, *This Journal*, 1944, **21**, 47.
2. D. Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, A1304.
3. Ray and Chowdhury, *This Journal*, 1950, **27**, 651.

hour in the cold, this was concentrated in a vacuum desiccator also in the cold, when reddish brown crystals separated out. These were filtered in a Gooch crucible, washed with cold water containing a few drops of nitric acid and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride and kept in the cold.

The compound is soluble in water and the solution undergoes decomposition on boiling. It is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, ether, diacetone alcohol and dimethyl formamide. The electrical conductivity of a $\cdot 001126M$ aqueous solution was found to be $335\cdot 1 \text{ cm}^2 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$. The substance is diamagnetic.

$\cdot 03915 \text{ g.}$ of the sample consumed $7\cdot 10 \text{ ml.}$ of $\cdot 01961N$ sodium thiosulphate solution. Calculated for the oxidimetric ($\text{Ag}^{III} \rightarrow \text{Ag}^I$) titration = $7\cdot 28 \text{ ml.}$

Found : Ag, 19·56; N, 32·45; NO_3^- , 33·36; $[\text{Ag}^{III}\text{Pipz}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ requires Ag, 19·69; N, 33·28; NO_3^- , 33·94%.

Silver (III) piperazine dibiguanide sulphate : This compound was prepared by treating a concentrated aqueous solution of the complex nitrate with cold dilute sulphuric acid when a red compound separated out. This was filtered, washed with ice-cold water and dried as in the previous case.

The substance is sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol, acetone and other common organic solvents. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid to form a red solution. The dry substance can be preserved unchanged for a long time in the cold. The substance is diamagnetic.

In the oxidimetric titration $\cdot 04310 \text{ g.}$ of the sample consumed $9\cdot 00 \text{ ml.}$ of $\cdot 01961N$ sodium thiosulphate solution. Calculated for the oxidimetric ($\text{Ag}^{III} \rightarrow \text{Ag}^I$) titration = $8\cdot 70 \text{ ml.}$

Found : Ag, 21·55; N, 27·35; $\text{SO}_4^{=}$, 28·48; H_2O , 1·90 (100°), $[\text{Ag}^{III}\text{Pipz}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1\cdot 5}$, $0\cdot 5 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 21·06; N, 27·40, $\text{SO}_4^{=}$, 28·29; H_2O , 1·76%.

Silver (III) piperazine dibiguanide hydroxide : The complex base was prepared by treating the cold solution of complex nitrate with potassium hydroxide solution till the pH of the system was about 9–9·5. A reddish brown precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass Gooch, washed with cold water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH.

The compound is sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, ether, dimethyl formamide and diacetone alcohol. It reacts strongly alkaline to litmus. When treated with dilute hydrochloric acid, it gives rise to an orange yellow precipitate which readily decomposes into white silver chloride. The compound can be heated upto 110° without any decomposition. The substance is diamagnetic.

In a typical oxidimetric titration $\cdot 03150 \text{ g.}$ of the sample consumed $7\cdot 60 \text{ ml.}$ of $\cdot 01961N$ sodium thiosulphate solution. Calculated for the oxidimetric ($\text{Ag}^{III} \rightarrow \text{Ag}^I$) titration = $7\cdot 78 \text{ ml.}$ (Found : Ag, 26·00; N, 34·55; H_2O , 13·22 (110°); $[\text{Ag}^{III}\text{Pipz}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_3$ requires Ag, 26·14; N, 33·91; H_2O , 13·10%).